

(Hf)PCN-224(Co) as an efficient ppm-level sensor for toxic SO₂

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ABSTRACT

Herein, we report the first experimental investigation, supported with theoretical calculations, of a porphyrin-based metal organic framework (PMOF) to address the difficult challenge of SO₂ detection and sensing. Specifically, the highly porous hafnium cobalt-porphyrin tetracarboxylate named (Hf)PCN-224(Co) was used as probe material. (Hf)PCN-224(Co) demonstrated a moderate SO₂ sorption of 1.0 mmol g⁻¹ at 0.1 bar and 298 K, and a limit of detection of 175.5 ppm, obtained by photoluminescent experiments. Furthermore, clear, different emission responses are observed for (Hf)PCN-224(Co) after the exposure to CO₂ and water vapor, compared to SO₂. Remarkably, (Hf)PCN-224(Co) shows crystalline retention after exposure to SO₂ at low concentrations (*i.e.*, 0.1 bar). The use of Hf⁴⁺, as well as microwave-assisted solvothermal synthesis, lead to crystalline defects in the form of missing linkers, providing additional Hf(IV) open metal sites, able to interact with SO₂ molecules. Based on UV-Vis and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopies, we suggest ligand to metal charge transfer as primal emission mechanisms, and the coordination of SO₂ with Hf₆(OH)₈ coordinatively unsaturated clusters as the most plausible origin for the emission response in SO₂ detection/sensing. The tendency of this behavior is verified from the density functional theory calculations.

1. Introduction

A nominated group of chemically stable metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) with large surface areas and a high degree of functionality has been postulated as promising candidates for the capture of highly corrosive gases (*e.g.*, SO₂, NO_x, NH₃ and H₂S) [1], since the adsorption selectivity of these molecules can be accurately adjusted as a function of the topology and chemical composition of their pores [2]. Such corrosive (and highly toxic) gases can permanently dislocate the coordination bonds between the polycomplexant organic ligands and the metal

centers of the MOF, triggering the collapse of its structure, as shown for MOF-177 [3]. Thus, the chemical stability of selected MOFs is then the essential prerequisite for the capture of these toxic gases, and remarkable examples have provided encouraging results, even under real working conditions (*i.e.* under moisture) [4].

Particularly, sulfur dioxide (SO₂) is categorized as one of the most corrosive and toxic chemicals, which can be easily absorbed by the respiratory system or dermal contact. Human exposure to SO₂ can cause drastic respiratory complications, principally in lung function (*i.e.*, broncho-constriction), and direct contact over 100 SO₂ ppm results

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deathly [5]. Although a selected group of MOFs have demonstrated outstanding SO_2 capture results [6,7], perhaps, the main disapproval of MOFs is the typical high cost of synthesis for the organic ligands and challenging scalability, which point out some of the flaws related to the economics of capturing SO_2 , at the industrial level, using MOFs. In this respect, it is worth to mention that the capture of SO_2 is not the only problem related to this toxic gas. The detection and quantification (sensing) of SO_2 in closed environments (e.g., laboratories, factories or industrial warehouses), results critical to protect the safety of the associated personnel to such places. For example, the concentration of SO_2 over periods of 10 min must not surpass 10 ppm, where the maximum regulated concentration limit is 0.075 ppm per hour [8]. Thus, specific research requires to be carefully dedicated to detecting SO_2 . One of the main advantages of using MOFs for detection purposes, conversely to SO_2 capture (large amounts of MOF are necessary), is that only small

amounts of a particular MOF are needed, minimizing the economic limitation and highlighting the health impact.

Among some effective strategies to detect gas molecules, optical methods such as ultraviolet (UV) absorption spectroscopy [9], multi-axis differential optical absorption spectroscopy (MAX-DOAS) [10], mass spectrometry [11], and photoluminescence spectroscopy (PL) [12] offer real-time gas monitoring. Thus, if a MOF shows photoluminescence properties, these could be modified before and after the exposure of a particular gas, such as SO_2 , and used as a transduction mechanism. If there is a clear fluorescent response to SO_2 (assuming the chemical stability of the MOF) this luminescent change represents the key to pave the way towards an effective SO_2 detector.

With these perspectives in mind, can eventually MOFs be manufactured into portable and low-cost SO_2 gas sensors to closely watch the safety of workers who are exposed to SO_2 due to different industrial

Fig. 1. a) Crystal structure of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) viewed along *a* axis. b) Close-up view of the crystal structure. It consists of TCPP(Co) coordinated via carboxylate groups to Hf₆(OH)₈ clusters. Color code: C=gray, O=red, N=purple, Co=Orange, Hf= blue. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

processes? One of the first demonstrations of a MOF-based SO₂ sensor (MFM-300) was elegantly delivered by Eddaoudi et al., exhibiting a detection limit of 5 ppb with facile cyclability [13]. Later, Cao and co-workers reported a detector based on the very well-known MOF-5-NH₂, by taking the approach of the turn-on photoluminescence response of to SO₂ and demonstrating stability under measurement conditions and therefore possible reusability (up to 6 cycles in solution-state experiments) [14].

Specifically, porphyrin-based MOFs have been widely investigated as probes in fluorescence sensing for cations, and anions, among other environmental pollutants [15,16]. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are not previous reports on porphyrin-based MOFs used as probes for SO₂ detection/sensing. Also note that some of these materials, particularly the one selected in this work, are currently being commercialized at industrial level (e.g., by CD Bioparticles Ltd.). Besides, novel green synthetic pathways that facilitate the industrial take-up of porphyrins have emerged in the last years [17], highlighting the relevance of these building units as a hot topic. For instance, specialized companies (e.g., PorphyChem SAS) commercialize these ligands in the large scale. We previously reported the synthesis, characterization, and catalytic properties of a microporous hafnium-based MOF entitled (Hf)PCN-224(Co) [18]. (Hf)PCN-224(Co) is built up from Hf₆(OH)₈ clusters linked by six square planar cobalt-metalated 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(4-carboxyphenyl) porphyrin, TCPP(Co) (Fig. 1). Herein, (Hf)PCN-224(Co) exhibited, by solid and solution-state fluorescence experiments, to be an effective detector and sensor for highly toxic SO₂ with a limit of detection (LOD) of 2.74 mM (~175 ppm) in solution-state. Thus, it is worth to mention that this is the first example where a porphyrin-based MOF is proposed as efficient SO₂ detector and sensor.

2. Methods

2.1. Reagents

Hafnium(IV) oxochloride octahydrate (HfOCl₂·8H₂O, 98 %) and cobalt(II) chloride (CoCl₂ anhydrous, 98 %) were from Sigma-Aldrich. Benzoic acid (99 %) was acquired from Acros Organics. The organic ligand 5,10,15,20-(tetra-4-carboxyphenyl)porphyrin (TCPP, >98 %) was from PorphyChem. Trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (triflic acid, >98 %) was from TCI Chemicals. Absolute ethanol was from VWR chemicals and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, >99 %) from Fischer Chemicals. Reagents were used as received without further purification.

2.2. Synthesis of (Hf)PCN-224(Co)

(Hf)PCN-224(Co) was synthesized according to our previously described microwave-assisted protocol [18]. Briefly, a preliminary metalation step was performed by mixing the ligand TCPP (192.4 mg, 0.24 mmol), anhydrous CoCl₂ (165.4 mg, 1.27 mmol) and 6 mL DMF in a 30 mL microwave glass vial and heated under predefined conditions (175 °C, 10 min, 600 rpm, 0.7 bar, 20 W) to give solution A. The cluster solution (B) was prepared in parallel, by mixing HfOCl₂·8H₂O (523.0 mg, 1.28 mmol) and benzoic acid (5.04 g, 41.27 mmol) in 6 mL. After dissolution, the mixture was heated in the microwave reactor (140 °C, 5 min, 600 rpm, 0.5 bar, <5 W). B was poured on A under continuous stirring, and then triflic acid was added to the reactor (0.6 mL, 6.77 mmol). MOF was obtained after heating the overall pre-polymerization mixture (150 °C, 30 min, 600 rpm, 3.6 bar, 10 W). The polymer was separated from the mother liquors by centrifuging (10000 rpm, 10 min) and then washed with DMF (2×30 mL) and absolute ethanol (3×30 mL). Finally, the resulting solid was dried under vacuum (100 °C, 12 h). (Hf)PCN-224(Co) (C₁₄₄H₇₂N₁₂Co₃O₆₄Hf₁₂; ICP-OES & CHNS elem. anal.: calc. 32.5 % C; 3.2 % N; 3.3 % Co; 40.3 % Hf. Exp.: 34.5 % C; 3.4 % N; 3.3 % Co; 39.7 % Hf) 275 mg, 51 % yield.

2.3. Characterization

Further details related to instrumental techniques are presented in supplementary material.

2.4. SO₂ capture and chemical stability after SO₂ exposure

SO₂ adsorption–desorption isotherm was obtained by using a Dynamic Gravimetric Gas/Vapor Sorption Analyzer, DVS vacuum (Surface Measurement Systems Ltd), and this isotherm was performed from 0 to 1 bar at 298 K on an activated sample (453 K for 12 h under 1.4 × 10⁻³ torr) of (Hf)PCN-224(Co). For chemical stability, crystallinity retention was used as parameter after the exposure to SO₂.

2.5. Electronic features and SO₂ detection/sensing

For detection and sensing, materials' activation was carried out by heating (Hf)PCN-224(Co) at 120 °C for 2 h under vacuum conditions. The exposure to SO₂ was carried out in our homemade *ex-situ* adsorption system (Fig. S1) for UV-Vis and solid-state photoluminescent spectroscopy.

UV-Vis absorption measurements were performed from 200 to 800 nm using a Shimadzu spectrophotometer UV-2600 equipped with an ISR-2600Plus integrating sphere and a BaSO₄ blank.

Fluorescence spectra were collected on a FS5 Edinburgh Instruments Spectrofluorometer using a continuous wave 150 W ozone-free xenon arc lamp at room temperature, coupled with the SC-10 Solid-state and SC-05 Standard Cuvette sample holder. The solid-state samples were packed into quartz sample holders and positioned into the instrument. For solution-state experiments 5 mg of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) were dispersed in 10 mL of THF. For LOD calculation, different titrations were made using SO₂ THF solution (0.5 M), and measured immediately after SO₂ solution addition, using quartz cuvettes. All spectra were acquired at ambient conditions (around 27 °C). Emission measurements were carried out using an excitation wavelength of 360 nm, with a LP-395 filter on the detector side to remove any remaining light from the excitation source. Emission spectra were collected with a step size of 1 nm and a dwell time of 0.1 s. The excitation bandwidth was set at 2.00 nm, and the emission bandwidth for the detector at 1.00 nm.

Time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) spectra were measured in an Edinburgh Instruments FS5 Spectrofluorometer using a 375 nm laser, with an excitation bandwidth of 0.01 nm and an emission bandwidth of 1 nm, at an emission wavelength of 450 nm.

2.6. Computational details

DFT calculations were performed at the B3LYP/LANL2DZ level of theory [19,20] using the Gaussian 09 software [21]. To confirm that the optimized geometries correspond to local minima, a frequency calculation was conducted to ensure the absence of imaginary frequencies. To study the stability of the interaction with the SO₂ molecule, the adsorption energies were calculated. Therefore, the contributions of the Gibbs free energies are considered in the following equation:

$$\Delta G_{\text{ad}} = G_{\text{interaction}} - [G_{\text{SO}_2} + G_{\text{cluster}}] \quad (1)$$

where $G_{\text{interaction}}$ is the Gibbs free energy of the formed system, the interaction between SO₂ molecule (G_{SO_2}) and cluster proposed, and the different cluster proposed (G_{cluster}). To investigate the electronic structure of these systems. For the lowest configuration, the natural charges and electron configurations were determined using the natural bond orbital (NBO) method [20]. To further examine the interaction between the SO₂ molecule and clusters, we analyzed the frontier molecular orbitals, including the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) (isosurfaces of 0.02 a.u.), as well as the density of states (DOS), using the MultiWFN 3.6

computational package [22].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization

(Hf)PCN-224(Co) was synthesized *via* microwave-assisted solvothermal method, showing great advantages over other approaches such as higher efficiency, faster reaction time, and lower cost, among others [23]. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) confirmed the cubic symmetry and the crystalline phase purity of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) (Fig. S2) [18,24], while the typical cubic morphology was revealed in the scanning electron micrographs (Fig. S3). Remarkably, high resolution SEM showed the truncated edges phenomenon related to the crystal growth in the presence of a large excess of modulator under microwave radiation, as previously described [25]. Later, a sample of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) was outgassed at 453 K for 12 h under vacuum (1.4×10^{-3} torr), to run a N₂ isotherm at 77 K (Fig. S4) which was used to estimate the total surface area, *i.e.*, BET (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller) surface area of 2380 ± 50 m² g⁻¹ with a pore size of 18.0 Å (Horvath-Kawazoe method considering a spherical pore geometry) and a pore volume of 1.24 cm³ g⁻¹. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and temperature-dependent PXRD for (Hf)PCN-224(Co), depicted in Fig. S5, indicate that this MOF collapsed at around 450 °C. By far, this is the highest thermal stability observed for porphyrin MOFs and comparable to that of the most stable well-known MOFs [26]. Chemical stability in aqueous media was demonstrated in a wide range of pH values (1–12) upon analyzing linker releasing by UV–Vis spectroscopy (see SI). Note that typical effluent outlets of processes involving SO₂ are released with a 30–35 % relative humidity at similar temperatures [27]. These aspects, together with the already demonstrated high affinity of cobalt towards CO₂ [18], suggested the potential use of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) as a promising candidate in SO₂ detection. Considering the large amount of defects found in (Hf)PCN-224(Co) determined by elemental analysis and TGA (see SI), typically found in materials synthesized under microwave radiation [28], it is expected an enhanced diffusion of gases throughout the MOF matrix and an increased availability of coordinatively unsaturated sites around structural metals, with a potential impact in SO₂ fixation.

3.2. SO₂ capture and chemical stability after SO₂ exposure

Fig. 2 shows the resulting isotherm obtained with a relatively fast SO₂ uptake from 0 to 0.05 bar of approximately 0.7 mmol g⁻¹. From

Fig. 2. SO₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm at 298 K up to 1 bar for activated (Hf)PCN-224(Co).

0.05 to 0.7 bar, the SO₂ adsorption isotherm exhibited an almost linear uptake with a total SO₂ amount of ≈ 3.5 mmol g⁻¹. Finally, a change on the shape of the isotherm is clearly observed, accounting for an almost plateau, leading to a total capacity (at 1 bar) of 4.0 mmol g⁻¹. The total SO₂ capture capacity of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) is considerably lower to representative chemically stable MOFs for SO₂ capture with similar BET surface areas (*e.g.* MIL-101(Cr)_4F) [7]. Thus, the structural stability following SO₂ adsorption/desorption was assessed by PXRD (see Fig. S8), showing that the crystal structure of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) was not retained.

Although this result corroborated the structural instability of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) upon exposure to a high concentration of SO₂ (*i.e.*, 1 bar), the most meaningful property of a MOF toward SO₂ detection is a high response to SO₂ at low concentrations since the sensing of SO₂ is commonly carried out at the ppm level [29]. Thus, the total SO₂ uptake at ambient pressure (1 bar = high concentration of SO₂) turn out to be irrelevant since, for example, flue gas exhibits SO₂ typical concentrations up to 10,000 ppm [30]. Thus, with this rationalizing in mind and considering that concentration ranges for SO₂ detection are at the ppm level, such ppm levels can be inherently correlated to the SO₂ low-pressure range (*e.g.*, from 0 to 0.1 bar). We decided to test the structure stability of an activated sample of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) which was only exposed to 0.1 bar of SO₂. PXRD patterns confirmed the retention of the crystalline structure (Fig. S9) after the SO₂ sorption experiment up to 0.1 bar. Therefore, to further corroborate the crystalline retention of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) towards SO₂ at relatively low concentrations, 5 adsorption-desorption isotherms were conducted from 0 to 0.1 bar, using a fresh sample, where the total SO₂ uptake remains practically the same in the 5 cycles (around 1.2 mmol g⁻¹), see Fig. S10. Additionally, PXRD pattern reveals that (Hf)PCN-224(Co) show partial amorphization as well as small shifts to higher angles, compared to the as-synthesized material, suggesting small changes in cell parameters, see Fig. S11. Hence, since SO₂ capture is similar for all cycles and PXRD patterns are essentially retained, it is possible to establish that (Hf)PCN-224(Co) is stable towards SO₂ at low concentrations.

3.3. Electronic features and SO₂ detection/sensing

Once it was established that the SO₂ adsorption up to 0.1 bar did not affect the crystalline structure of (Hf)PCN-224(Co), we decided to evaluate its use as a fluorescent SO₂ detector. As a first approach to understand the electronic features of (Hf)PCN-224(Co), UV–Vis spectra of an activated and an exposed to SO₂ at 0.1 bar samples were acquired (Fig. 3a). According to Fig. 3a–(Hf)PCN-224(Co) shows broad absorption bands in the full UV–Vis range, as previously reported for porphyrin-based MOFs [31]. This feature is the result of the conjugated π -bonds in TCPP linker. Thus, electronic transitions might arise mainly due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. In addition, two regions, from 360 to 410 nm and from 440 to 650 nm, are highlighted: the former is called the Soret band (or B band) ($S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transitions) and the second region is named the Q band ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transitions) [32]. According to Gouterman's four orbital model (Fig. 3b), absorption bands in free-base porphyrins appear due to transition from the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMO) to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMO) (Fig. 3c). The HOMO orbitals are a_{1u} and a_{2u} , and the LUMO orbitals are e_{gx} and e_{gy} [33]. The presence of Co²⁺ coordinated to nitrogen increases the ring symmetry, from D_{2h} in metal-free porphyrin to D_{4h} in metalated-porphyrin. Consequently, only two bands are observed for (Hf)PCN-224(Co) in the Q band region [32]. Since in solid-state spectroscopy samples are measured in high concentrations, extra precautions should be taken because additional transitions could be neglected, aspect of particular relevance in the case of (Hf)PCN-224(Co), which is a dark powdered material. Furthermore, porphyrin-based MOFs usually show other electronic phenomena, *e.g.*, ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) [34] or Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET) [35], which can also be neglected in the solid-state UV–Vis spectra. Fig. 3a shows that

Fig. 3. a) Solid-state UV-Vis spectra of activated and exposed (Hf)PCN-224(Co) to SO_2 at 0.1 bar. Regions for transitions from ground singlet state (S_0) to first (S_1) and second singlet excited state (S_2) are highlighted. b) Gouterman's HOMO (a_{2u} and a_{1u}) and LUMO (e_{gx} and e_{gy}) frontier molecular orbitals for free-base porphyrins. c) Electronic transitions between HOMO and LUMO frontier orbitals, as well as Q and Soret bands transitions. d) Fluorescence emission spectra of activated and SO_2 exposed samples. e) Solid-state lifetime of activated and SO_2 exposed samples. f) Solution-state emission spectrum of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) titrated with SO_2 solution.

absorption intensity decreases for SO_2 exposed sample and, although this decrease is very clear, the spectrum profile practically does not get modified. This outcome indicates that SO_2 molecules interact electronically with the material, limiting the absorption process.

The excitation spectra maximum was found at 360 nm (Fig. S12). Thus, recording every emission spectrum at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 360$ nm gives the maximum emission intensities for all radiative relaxation-transitions. A broad emission spectrum from the activated material, from 380 to 650 nm (Fig. 3d), was obtained with a maximum emission at $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 475$ nm, which is similar to previously reported Zr-based PCN-224 MOF [34]. No

emission bands around 600–800 nm (Q-bands-related emission, $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$) are observed, which can be attributed to the coordination of Co^{2+} to TCPP linker [36]. Thus, the maximum emission wavelength (475 nm) and the absence of emission from Q-bands might suggest that emission appears purely from LMCT process between oxygen from TCPP and Hf^{4+} cations, where LMCT emission for (Zr)PCN-224 has previously reported [34]. Due to the lower electronegativity of Hf(IV) in comparison to Zr (IV), an enhanced molecular orbital overlap would appear for Hf-O coordination bonds, and, as consequence, an enhancement of LMCT transition might arise [37].

For solid-state SO₂ detection purposes, another activated sample of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) was exposed to 0.1 bar of SO₂ to measure its photoluminescence properties. As it can be observed, a clear change in the fluorescent intensity was recorded (49.7 % decrease) after SO₂ exposure (Fig. 3d). This turn-off effect is associated to the changes in the electronic structure of (Hf)PCN-224(Co), in good correlation with the UV-Vis spectrum, *vide infra*.

Finally, the effect of saturation with CO₂ and water vapor on the fluorescence of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) was tested in the solid-state to compare it with the effect of SO₂ (Fig. S13). Notice that, although both molecules generate changes in fluorescence, these are different from that generated by SO₂. To begin with, the fluorescence generated by saturation with water is comparable, almost identical to the fluorescence of the material synthesized before activation. It is hypothesized that the marked difference between the intensities and shapes of the emission spectra of the material before and after activation is due to the loss of ethanol molecules, coming from the solvent used for the synthesis, coordinated to the Co(II) centers and which, subsequently, after activation ended up unsaturated. Alternatively, it would be expected that upon exposure of the activated material to water vapor, these molecules replace the coordinated ethanol molecules, to the Co(II) metal centers. The reason for the weak fluorescence emission in both cases can be related to the hydrogen bonds that may be occurring between the respective Co(II)-coordinated molecules, since it has been reported in the literature that there may be hydrogen-bond-assisted non-radiative deactivation of fluorescence [38]. On the other hand, the effect on the fluorescence generated by CO₂ is similar to that of SO₂ in terms of shape and intensity of the spectrum, which can be related to the fact that SO₂ and CO₂ do not generate hydrogen bonds with each other and also prefer to interact with Hf(IV) since this metal shows a much higher Lewis acid character than Co(II). Since clear different responses were shown after the exposure to different gases, it is expected that no important interferences would appear in real-life applications.

Lifetime measurements for the (Hf)PCN-224(Co) before and after exposition to SO₂ 0.1 bar are shown in Fig. 3c. A slight decrease in lifetime was found from 1.8138 ns for the activated material to 1.3984 ns for (Hf)PCN-224(Co) exposed to SO₂ at 0.1 (Table S2), demonstrating that the fluorescence quenching is not driven by dynamic mechanisms but by static ones.

LOD was accomplished by solution-state experiments in THF (Fig. 3d). Evidently, a quenching phenomenon, as function of concentration, is observed. Interestingly, the first emission intensity decreases just at 1.6 mM (102.5 ppm) and continues up to 9.6 mM (615.0 ppm), indicating that (Hf)PCN-224(Co) can be used quantitatively for SO₂ sensing in the ppm range. Moreover, blank standard deviation is of only 2.94 %, evidencing the high reliability of the (Hf)PCN-224(Co) as sensing probe (Fig. S14). Finally, the LOD was estimated as relatively low as 175.5 ppm (Fig. S15), making (Hf)PCN-224(Co) competitive to other MOFs previously reported, see Table S3. Specifically, MOFs previously reported to be used as probes to detect SO₂, sense in ppm concentration range, as in the case of (Hf)PCN-224(Co). Additionally, some MOFs have not been analyzed to demonstrate chemical stability towards SO₂. Furthermore, some measurements are made using SO₃²⁻, and HSO₃⁻, instead of SO₂, and their selectivity tests are made again other ionic species instead of other gases that could be present in real-life situations, in contrast to (Hf)PCN-224(Co).

3.4. Interaction of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) with SO₂ and suggested sensing mechanism

To elucidate the interaction mechanism of SO₂ with (Hf)PCN-224(Co), X-ray photoelectron spectrum (XPS) was carried out. Thus, an activated and an exposed to SO₂ at 0.1 bar samples were measured by XPS. The survey spectra (Fig. S16) shows that sulfur species are present after SO₂ exposure, which indicates the reliability of using this technique to study the electronic interactions of SO₂ with the atoms within

the material framework. As previously discussed, emission phenomenon can be related to LMCT transitions between oxygen and hafnium. Additionally, SO₂ is expected to electronically interact with Co(II), and may even coordinate to it, since Co(II) coordinated to pyrrole rings of the TCPP linker displays a quasi-square planar geometry [39]. This coordination environment leaves available orbitals, allowing further ligand binding. Additionally, coordination of the guest molecules to metalated porphyrin-based MOFs is a well-known phenomenon, *e.g.*, in catalytic processes [40]. Thus, the high-resolution spectra of Hf 4f and Co 2p of both samples were fitted and compared, see Fig. 4a and b. The narrow Hf 4f spectrum of the activated sample exhibits two main peaks at 17.5 and 19.2 eV, assigned to Hf 4f_{7/2} and Hf 4f_{5/2} [41]. For (Hf)PCN-224(Co) exposed to SO₂, a clear binding energy shift is observed, indicating a change in the electron density around Hf(IV) [42]. This result suggests a strong interaction between SO₂ molecules and Hf(IV). For the Co 2p, the high-resolution spectrum shows significantly split spin-orbit components at 780.5 and 795.7 eV, corresponding to Co 2p_{5/2} and Co 2p_{3/2}, respectively [36,43]. The presence of Co(II) is evidenced by observable satellite features around 787 and 804 eV [44], and after SO₂ exposure, (Hf)PCN-224(Co) Co 2p spectrum shifts 0.1 and 0.2 eV. Although only a small binding energy shift is observed, clear profile changes are observed in the whole spectrum. Furthermore, previous theoretical studies evidenced the interaction of SO₂ molecules with Co(II) centers in porphyrin rings [45]. Thus, both results suggest interaction of the SO₂ molecules with Hf(IV) and Co(II) metals. Regarding Hf(IV), the secondary building unit (SBU) of (Hf)PCN-224(Co) comprises Hf₆(OH)₈ clusters, which are coordinated to six TCPP(Co) linkers (Fig. 4c). It is known that PCN-224 materials, porphyrin-based MOFs, as well as M(IV)-based MOFs, often exhibit crystallographic defects, *i.e.*, missing linkers, which can provide open metal sites as Hf(IV) centers [46–49]. Furthermore, microwave-assisted synthesis enhances the accessibility of open metal sites in the form of missing linkers [28]. Herein, we propose that Hf(IV) open metal sites, which work as a Lewis base, are able to coordinate SO₂ molecules (Fig. 4d). Indeed, SO₂ coordination limits LMCT between oxygen and hafnium, since orbitals of Hf(IV) are more occupied after SO₂ coordination. The restricted orbitals lead to less excited species and, consequently, to less emission intensity, as seen in Fig. 3a and e.

3.5. DFT calculations

In order to evaluate the affinity of the metal center of the (Hf)PCN-224(Co) to adsorb the SO₂ molecule from the atomistic point of view, DFT-based calculations were carried out to corroborate the influence of these metallic centers (Hf and Co). Here, from the crystallographic archive [18], two characteristic molecular fragments of the MOF were identified: the first consists of an Hf cluster containing six transition metal atoms, and the second is a Co porphyrin. Based on these models, two clusters were proposed to represent the reactive site for SO₂ adsorption. The selection of structures is represented in Fig. 5a. From this structure, two molecular fragments called cluster 1 (PCN(Co)) and 2 ((Hf)PCN) are used, as shown in Fig. 5b and (c), respectively. Both structures are optimized at B3LP/LANL2DZ level of theory. For the PCN(Co) structure, it can be observed that the structural parameter between the N and Co atoms is 1.99 Å, which corroborates the signals identified from Co with the pyridine rings in the structure. In the case of (Hf)PCN, the formation of the Hf₆ cluster exhibits two distinct binding parameters: one corresponding to the O atoms of the pendant molecular benzene fragments (2.11 Å) and the other to the Hf-O bonds that form the cluster (2.05 Å) as shown in Fig. 5c. It is worth noting that the PCN(Co) and (Hf)PCN structures exhibit symmetry groups of D₄ and D_{3d}, respectively. Based on optimized geometries, the interaction of the SO₂ molecule with the metal centers (Co and Hf) was analyzed to determine the optimal adsorption site with good affinity within the MOF. Table S4 presents the adsorption energy values (ΔG_{ad}) for the SO₂/PCN(Co) and SO₂/(Hf)PCN configurations. According to the negative values ΔG_{ad} of

Fig. 4. a) High-resolution XPS spectra of Hf 4f. b) High-resolution XPS spectra of Co 2p. c) SBU coordinated to six TCPP(Co) linkers. d) Missing linker defect in (Hf)PCN-224(Co), as well as schematic representation of possible interaction/coordination of SO₂ with Hf(IV) and Co(II). Color code: C=gray, O=red, N=purple, Hf=blue, Co=orange, S= yellow and H=white. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

the adsorption energies, it can be seen that the interaction of the SO₂ molecule with the MOF has an exergonic character for both cases. However, it is possible to see that the interaction on the (Hf)PCN cluster has a greater covalent attraction compared to that of the PCN(Co) system. This behavior may be due to the fact that the SO₂ molecule undergoes an elongation in the bonding length (S-O), this can be observed in Fig. 5(d–e). In addition, the interaction distance between the oxygen atom and the metal center is shorter for the O-Hf (1.88 Å) case than for the O-Co (1.91 Å) porphyrin system, hence, corroborating the XPS results.

To understand the electronic effect on the absorption of the SO₂ molecule in the study clusters, an NBO analysis was carried out on the metal centers of each interaction. Table S5 shows the natural configuration of the metallic centers before and after SO₂ adsorption. Here, a decrease in the charge population can be seen during the adsorption of SO₂, with the atomic orbitals 3d4p and 5d6p affected for Co and Hf, respectively. The charge transfer at the metal centers is relatively similar in both cases, mainly influenced by the 3d and 5d atomic orbitals, which enhance interaction with the 2p orbitals of the oxygen atoms. To assess the efficiency of this interaction between the SO₂ molecule and the metal centers, an electron localization function (ELF) analysis was performed on the interaction plane. Fig. 6 presents the 2D ELF maps over the metal centers and the oxygen atom of the SO₂ molecule. The ELF describes the efficiency of Pauli repulsion at a given point in real molecular space [50]. Fig. 6b, depicting the interaction of the SO₂/(Hf) PCN system, favors a greater electronic localization between the O-Hf bond (green regions), compared to the O-Co interaction where blue regions can be seen between the cluster and the SO₂ molecule (see Fig. 6a). This behavior corroborates the high adsorption energy value (−5.86 eV) reported for the SO₂/(Hf)PCN system. Finally, the contribution of the frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) formed is analyzed from the PDOS

diagrams as shown in Fig. S17. For the SO₂/PCN(Co) system, the formation of a wide energy gap between the HOMO-LUMO levels (1.95 eV) can be observed. Here, the HOMO and LUMO contribution is majority by the PCN(Co) cluster. In the case of the SO₂/(Hf)PCN system, it presents a small HOMO-LUMO energy gap (0.79 eV). It is worth noting that the HOMO contributions come from the SO₂ molecule, while the LUMO is very well localized in the (Hf)PCN cluster. This behavior suggests that the MOF ultimately exhibits a charge-accepting character during SO₂ adsorption. However, the elongation of SO₂ bonds in the SO₂/(Hf)PCN system suggests potential catalytic activity at this site within the MOF structure. As it can be seen, SO₂ interacts strongly electronically with Hf(IV), which leads to reduce the LMCT transitions between oxygen from TCPP linkers and Hf(IV), since Hf(IV) orbitals are already occupied by SO₂ molecules, thus confirming the proposed sensing mechanism in section 3.4. Additionally, since we expect the presence of open metal sites in Hf₆(OH)₈ clusters, SO₂ might coordinate “easier” to Hf(IV) centers, compared (Hf)PCN-224(Co) without defects, *i.e.*, without open metal sites, conducting to an even more restricted LMCT emission.

4. Conclusions

To summarize, we report the first experimental investigation on the detection and sensing of SO₂ on a porphyrin-based MOF, the microporous hafnium cobalt-porphyrin tetracarboxylate (Hf)PCN-224(Co). While the SO₂ uptake of 4.00 mmol g^{−1} (298 K and 1 bar) does not rival the other leading MOFs, and (Hf)PCN-224(Co) is structurally unstable at high pressures (1 bar), (Hf)PCN-224(Co) shows crystalline retention at low concentrations typically found for detection purposes (0.1 bar). Interestingly, using Hf⁴⁺ as MOF constitutive metal and the microwave-assisted solvothermal synthesis lead to Hf(IV) open metal sites in the resulting MOF, due to the intrinsic formation of defects, which is the key

Fig. 5. Geometry optimization of molecular configurations provide the (a) (Hf)PCN-224(Co) structure (b) PCN(Co) and (c) (Hf)PCN show the molecular structure derived from the metallic centers of Hf and Co, respectively. (d) SO₂/PCN(Co), and (e) SO₂/(Hf)PCN geometry configuration of the SO₂ molecule adsorbed on the Co and Hf systems, respectively.

for the efficient detection and sensing of SO₂ at ppm-level (limit of detection = 175.5 ppm), providing a promising practical SO₂ sensor. Additionally, when compared the SO₂ emission spectra to emission spectra of CO₂ and water vapor, clear differences are observed, indicating the good selectivity of (Hf)PCN-224(Co). Furthermore, DFT calculations indicate the strong adsorption of the SO₂ molecule on the metal centers of the MOF, exhibiting a stronger affinity ($\Delta G_{ad} = -5.86$ eV) for the Hf cluster. Finally, we believe that the implementation of porphyrin-based materials in sensor and catalytic devices due to their relevant photoelectronic features will compensate the production cost in the large scale of both starting materials and final products in the near future, as observed in the case of terephthalate-based MOFs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sergio Carrasco: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Marco L. Martínez:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Yoarhy A. Amador-Sánchez:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Valeria B. López Cervantes:** Investigation, Data curation. **Elí Sánchez-González:** Methodology,

Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nora S. Portillo-Vélez:** Validation, Data curation. **Ricardo A. Peralta:** Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Christian A. Celaya:** Data curation, Investigation, Software, Writing – review & editing. **Ariel Guzmán-Vargas:** Resources, Project administration. **Patricia Horcajada:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Diego Solís-Ibarra:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Ilich A. Ibarra:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Fig. 6. Electron localization function (ELF) for the systems under study: (a) $\text{SO}_2/\text{PCN}(\text{Co})$ and (b) $\text{SO}_2/(\text{Hf})\text{PCN}$ systems. The ELF values range from 0.0 to 1.0, with 1 (red) indicating complete localization, and 0 (blue) corresponding to the absence of electron distribution. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Ilich A. Ibarra reports financial support was provided by UNAM. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix. ASupplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtadv.2025.100579>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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